

Additional file 4: Table S3. Mass spectrometry analysis of normalized celulosomal proteins.

The intensities of all the proteins in four celulosomal fractions (CB I, CB II, MCC I and MCC II) were estimated by iBAQ and LFQ methods, in order to evaluate their quantity and abundance. The iBAQ intensities were normalized by dividing each value by that of the major primary scaffoldin ScaA1 in each sample, in order to facilitate interpretation of the results and relate the celulosomal proteins to the major primary scaffoldin within the samples. The LFQ intensities were normalized by dividing the values by the intensity of ScaA1 in CB I, in order to simplify the fold-change analysis between the different samples. **A.** Identified scaffoldins in each fraction. **B.** 166 identified dockerin-containing proteins. CB, cellobiose; MCC, microcrystalline cellulose; Doc, dockerin; GH, glycoside hydrolase; CBM, carbohydrate-binding module; CE, carbohydrate esterase; PL, polysaccharide lyases. Significant iBAQ values (≥ 0.10) are shown in bold. The range of LFQ values is color coded according to the scale shown at the bottom.

A.

Gene name	Scaffoldin name	iBAQ Values				LFQ Values			
		iBAQ CB I	iBAQ CB II	iBAQ MCC I	iBAQ MCC II	LFQ CB I	LFQ CB II	LFQ MCC I	LFQ MCC II
Bccel_2050	ScaA1	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.000	0.160	1.303	0.302
Bccel_1393	ScaA2	0.09	0.02	0.33	0.16	0.084	0.006	0.516	0.071
Bccel_2049	ScaB	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.033	0.009	0.028	0.010
Bccel_3672	ScaE	1.89	3.71	1.34	2.22	1.262	0.399	1.261	0.490
Bccel_0335	ScaF1	0.56	0.12	0.18	0.16	0.139	0.006	0.060	0.012
Bccel_1026	ScaF2	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.010	0.004	0.002	0.003
Bccel_1881	ScaG	0.02	2.79	0.01	1.67	0.008	0.114	0.004	0.154
Bccel_5400	ScaH2	0.12	1.87	0.29	1.62	0.016	0.047	0.036	0.096
Bccel_3452	ScaH3	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.006	0.003	0.004	0.002
Bccel_1798	ScaI	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.001	0.001	0.004	0.003
Bccel_1025	ScaJ	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.02	0.003	0.002	0.001	0.003
Bccel_2276	ScaL1	0.04	0.27	0.02	0.20	0.005	0.013	0.004	0.015
Bccel_2277	ScaL2	0.22	0.16	0.36	0.44	0.049	0.007	0.094	0.038
Bccel_4693	ScaM1	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.012	0.006	0.011	0.005
Bccel_3957	ScaM2	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002
Bccel_3191	ScaO	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.001
Bccel_5402	ScaO2	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.08	0.001	0.005	0.002	0.015
Bccel_5008	ScaP	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000
Bccel_1808	ScaS	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.020	0.000	0.007	0.000
Bccel_5396	ScaT	0.01	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001
Bccel_0665	ScaU	0.05	0.09	0.01	0.05	0.020	0.010	0.008	0.011
Bccel_1669	ScaV	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Bccel_1027	ScaW1	0.01	0.06	0.00	0.01	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Bccel_2278	ScaW2	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.02	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001
					0	0.001	0.01	0.1	1

